

Synthesis and characterization of a mononuclear and a dinuclear complex of Cu^{II} with (*E*)-2-((pyridine-2-yl)methyleneamino)benzenethiol ligand

M. Choudhary^{*a}, K. Ahmad^a, S. R. Sharma^a, S. P. Rawat^b, S. S. Saket^c and D. P. Prajapati^d

^aDepartment of Chemistry, National Institute of Technology, Patna-800 005, Bihar, India

E-mail : mukesh@nitp.ac.in

^bDepartment of Chemistry, Govt. V. P.G. College, Maihar-485 771, Madhya Pradesh, India

^cDepartment of Chemistry, Govt. S. G. S. P.G. College, Sidhi-486 661, Madhya Pradesh, India

^dDepartment of Chemistry, Govt. P.G. College, Seoni-480 661, Madhya Pradesh, India

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Abstract : Mononuclear Cu^{II} complex, [Cu(L¹)(H₂O)Cl] **1** and dinuclear complex [Cu₂(L¹)₂(Cl)₂] **2**, derived from (*E*)-2-((pyridine-2-yl)methyleneamino)benzenethiol (L¹H), was synthesized and characterized by various physico-chemical and spectroscopic techniques. IR spectra, electronic spectra and EPR spectroscopy of the complex **1** suggested a square pyramidal geometry around Cu^{II} ion. The two copper ions were penta-coordinated with distorted square pyramidal geometries for **2**. The magnetic measurements of di-copper complex **2** exhibited the presence of antiferromagnetic exchange interaction between Cu^{II}-Cu^{II} ions. The synthesized L¹H ligand was bound with the Cu^{II} ion in a tridentate manner, with SNN donor sites. The EPR spectra of Cu^{II} complexes provide information of about the extent of the delocalization of the unpaired electrons, indicating $d_{x^2-y^2}$ ground state. The half-wave potential values for Cu^{II}/Cu^I redox couple obtained in aqueous solution as well as the reaction of the copper complexes with molecular oxygen and superoxide (O₂⁻) radical elongated in DMSO are in agreement with the SOD-like activity of the copper(II) complexes.

Keywords : Mono-/dinuclear, copper, EPR spectra, SOD activity, Schiff base, coordination chemistry.

Introduction

Transition metal complexes with tridentate Schiff base ligands have been widely investigated since such ligands can bind with one, two or more metal centres involving various chelation modes and thus allow the successful synthesis of metal complexes with interesting stereochemistry and model enzymes. A large number of Schiff bases and their complexes may exhibit properties such as reversible binding of oxygen, transfer of amino group, varied complexing/redox abilities, and as nano-precursors. The Schiff bases have high affinity for Cu^{II} ions; hence exhibit potential application in various areas¹⁻⁶. Chelating ligands with NNS donors are important in coordination chemistry owing to their stability, chemical properties, electrochemical activities, and broad biological activities. Coordination chemistry of copper with (*E*)-2-((pyridine-2-yl)methyleneamino)benzenethiol ligand is interesting as their molecular structures, spectral properties,

redox properties and medical applications mimic those of sulphur containing proteins⁷.

Kumar *et al.*⁸ have studied synthesis, spectral and solution studies of some homo-binuclear Cu^{II}-Cu^{II} and hetero-binuclear Cu^{II}-Zn^{II} homologue. Magnetic moment value of homo-binuclear complexes indicates the antiferromagnetic interactions. Patel *et al.*^{9,10} have reported the X-band EPR spectra of polycrystalline sample of some Cu^{II} mononuclear and Cu^{II}-Cu^{II}/Cu^{II}-Ni^{II} binuclear complexes using tridentate and monodentate ligands.

There are many papers^{11,12} describing magnetic interactions in Cu^{II} complexes, mediated via mono- and multi-atomic bridged ligands. However, studies on complexes wherein the interactions are primarily via weak intermolecular in nature are rare scarce. In such systems, EPR is an ideal, complimentary technique to study magnetic properties¹³.

The catalytic activities of copper(II) complexes mimicking the superoxide dismutase (SOD) activity provide models for metallo-proteins active sites and lend insight toward the design of new catalysts¹⁴⁻¹⁶. Copper is a biologically relevant element and many enzymes that depend on copper for their activity have been identified. Among these complexes, copper(II) complexes are known to play a significant role in naturally occurring biological systems¹⁷, like (Cu, Zn-SOD) superoxide dismutase. These SODs disproportionate the toxic O_2^- to molecular oxygen and hydrogen peroxide¹⁸⁻²⁰. All SOD employ the two step Ping-Pong mechanism shown in eqs. (1) and (2), where M is the redox active metal centre capable of both oxidizing and reducing superoxide activity.

With this point in view, we report here, synthesis and characterization of mononuclear and a binuclear complex of Cu^{II} with a tridentate Schiff base, (*E*)-2-((pyridine-2-yl)methyleneamino)benzenethiol ligand. The complexes was formulated as mononuclear complex $[Cu(L^1)(H_2O)Cl]$ **1** and binuclear complex $[Cu_2(L^1)_2(Cl)_2]$ **2**. The synthesized L^1H ligand was bound with the Cu^{II} ion in a tridentate manner, with SNN donor sites of the benzenethiol-S, azomethine-N, and pyridine-N atoms (Scheme 1). The SOD activities of the complexes have also been investigated by NBT assay method.

Scheme 1. Synthesis of (*E*)-2-((pyridine-2-yl)methyleneamino)benzenethiol (L^1H).

Experimental

Materials used for synthesis :

All the chemicals and solvents used were synthetic grade and used without further purification.

Physical measurements :

Elemental analyses were performed on an Elementar Vario EL III Carlo Erba 1108 analyzer. FAB mass spectra were recorded on a JEOL SX 102/DA 6000 Mass

spectrometer using argon/xenon (6 kV, 10 mA) as the FAB gas. The accelerating voltage was 10 kV and the spectra were recorded at room temperature (RT). Magnetic susceptibility measurements were performed on a Gouy balance at RT using $Hg[Co(SCN)_4]$ as calibrating agent. The molar conductance measurements were realized using 10^{-3} M solution of the complexes in DMSO on conductivity bridge at room temperature. The electronic spectra (in DMSO) were recorded on a Shimadzu UV-Vis spectrophotometer. FT-IR spectra were recorded in KBr discs on a Perkin-Elmer 783 spectrophotometer in wave number range $4000-400\ cm^{-1}$. X-band EPR spectra were recorded at room temperature on a Varian E-line Century Series spectrometer operating in the X-band region with 100 kHz modulation frequency, 5 mW microwave power and 1 G modulation amplitude was using tetracyano-ethylene (TCNE) as the internal standard. Cyclic voltammetry was performed with a BAS-100 Epsilon electrochemical analyser using a three-electrode electrochemical cell. Ag/AgCl was used as a reference electrode, glassy carbon as the working electrode and a platinum wire as the auxiliary electrode. 0.1 M $NaClO_4$ was used as the supporting electrolyte and DMSO as the solvent. The *in vitro* SOD activity was measured using alkaline DMSO as a source of superoxide radical (O_2^-) and nitrobluetetrazolium chloride (NBT) as O_2^- scavenger^{21,22}.

Preparations :

Synthesis of (*E*)-2-((pyridine-2-yl)methyleneamino)benzenethiol :

The (*E*)-2-((pyridine-2-yl)methyleneamino)benzenethiol was synthesized by the condensation of an equimolar ratio of picolinaldehyde (1.0 mmol, 0.170 g) with 2-aminobenzenethiol (1.0 mmol, 0.109 mL) dissolved in ethanol (Scheme 1) for 4–6 h at 60 °C. The resulting reaction mixture was refluxed on a water bath for 4 h and then allowed to cool overnight. The colored crystalline solid of the obtained Schiff base was filtered, washed with cold ethanol several times and dried in air at room temperature and finally preserved under reduced pressure in a desiccator. Yield : ~ 85%. The elemental analysis and FAB-mass (m/z) spectral outputs of Schiff base was given in Table 1.

Table 1. Analytical data of Schiff base ligand (L¹H) and their mononuclear and dinuclear Cu^{II} complexes

HL ² and Compds.	Empirical formula	Analytical data (%) : Calcd. (Found)			FAB-mass (<i>m/z</i>) %
		C	H	N	Calcd. (Found)
L ¹ H	C ₁₂ H ₁₀ N ₂ S	67.28 (67.30)	4.67 (4.69)	13.08 (13.09)	214 (215)
[Cu(L ¹)Cl].H ₂ O 1	C ₁₂ H ₁₁ ClCuN ₂ OS	43.90 (43.92)	3.35 (3.37)	8.53 (8.55)	338 (339)
[Cu ₂ (L ¹) ₂ (Cl) ₂] 2	C ₂₄ H ₁₈ Cl ₂ Cu ₂ N ₄ S ₂	46.45 (46.47)	2.90 (2.92)	10.96 (10.98)	620 (621)

Synthesis of complexes :

The complexes were prepared by the following general procedure :

Synthesis of mononuclear complex [Cu(L¹)(H₂O)Cl] 1 and dinuclear complex [Cu₂(L¹)₂(Cl)₂] 2 :

Mononuclear Cu^{II} complex [Cu(L¹)(H₂O)(Cl)] **1** was prepared by mixing 50 mL of a 10 mM basic ethanolic solution of copper(II) chloride dihydrate (1.0 mmol, 0.170 g) with 50 mL of a 10 mM ethanolic solution of the (*E*)-2-((pyridine-2-yl)methyleneamino)benzenethiol ligand (1.0 mmol, 0.214 g) in a 1 : 1 (metal-ligand) ratio. The resulting mixture was refluxed on a water bath for 3–5 h. A blue coloured complex **1** was appeared on standing and cooling the solution. Yield : 70%.

Dinuclear complex [Cu₂(L¹)₂(Cl)₂] **2** was prepared similar fashion by mixing 50 mL of a 10 mM basic ethanolic solution of copper(II) chloride dehydrate (10 mmol, 0.170 g) with 50 mL of a 20 mM ethanolic solution of the Schiff base (2.0 mmol, 0.428 g) was added with constant stirring at 100 °C in a 1 : 2 (metal-ligand) ratio. The resulting mixture was refluxed on a water bath for 2–4 h. A coloured products appeared on standing and cooling the solution. The precipitated complexes were filtered, washed with ether and recrystallizes several times from ethanol and dried under reduced pressure over anhydrous CaCl₂ in a desiccator. This complex was further dried in an electric oven at 50 °C. Yield : 65%. The elemental analysis and FAB-mass (*m/z*) spectral outputs of copper complexes was given in Table 1.

Results and discussion*Synthesis and characterization :*

The metal chelates had 1 : 1 or 1 : 2 stoichiometry by reacting metal(II) salt with (*E*)-2-((pyridine-2-yl)methyleneamino)benzenethiol. The complexes were synthesized by following sequential routes,

In the present research paper, the coordination behaviour of Schiff base, (*E*)-2-((pyridine-2-yl)methyleneamino)benzenethiol (Scheme 1), derived from the condensation of piconaldehyde with 2-aminobenzenethiol, towards Cu^{II} ion is described, which may help in more understanding of the mode of chelation of ligands towards copper(II) complexes. The proposed structures of a mononuclear and a dinuclear complex of Cu^{II} of L¹H were given in Scheme 2. The elemental analysis and spectroscopic data of the mononuclear complex suggested a

Scheme 2. Proposed structures of mononuclear and dinuclear Schiff base complexes of L¹H.

square pyramidal geometry for **1** around Cu^{II} ion. The two copper ions were penta-coordinated with distorted square pyramidal geometries for **2**. The magnetic measurements of di-copper (chloro-bridge copper centre) **2** exhibited the presence of antiferromagnetic exchange interaction. All the copper complexes were coloured, solid and stable towards air and moisture at RT. IR spectra suggest that the L¹H coordinated with the Cu^{II} ion in a

tridentate manner, with SNN donor sites of the benzenethiol-S, azomethine-N, and pyridine-N atoms. The observed molar conductance of the complexes in DMSO at room temperature was found at the range 2.56–6.85 $\Omega^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1} \text{ mol}^{-1}$ of 10^{-3} M solutions of the complexes in DMSO at room temperature indicate that they are non-electrolytes²³.

FAB-mass spectra :

The FAB-mass spectra suggested that the present mononuclear Cu^{II} complex of L^1H have a monomeric nature whereas binuclear complex showed dimeric nature. Both complexes showed molecular ion peaks in good agreement with the empirical formula of which was given in Table 1. Thus, mass spectra of the complexes $[\text{Cu}(\text{L}^1)(\text{H}_2\text{O})\text{Cl}]$ **1** and $[\text{Cu}_2(\text{L}^1)_2(\text{Cl})_2]$ **2**, as representative complexes, showed the highest mass peaks at m/z at 339 and 621, respectively, which agree well with the formula weights of the complexes²⁴.

Magnetic susceptibility measurements :

Room temperature magnetic susceptibility data of the complexes are measured on powdered samples of the complexes. The observed magnetic moments (μ_{eff}) of Cu^{II} mononuclear **1** is 1.82 B.M. and is in agreement with a one spin system ($s = 1/2$). The value of magnetic moment for this complex was 1.82 B.M., thus square pyramidal geometry²⁵ is suggested for the Cu^{II} complex. In the case of $\text{Cu}^{\text{II}}\text{-Cu}^{\text{II}}$ binuclear complex **2**, the effective magnetic moment values of 1.77 B.M., might indicate anti-ferromagnetic interactions^{26,27}, at room temperature, suggesting dimeric structures that is bridging of the Cu^{II} ions through the deprotonated sulphur atom. Similar magnetic behaviours of $\text{Cu}^{\text{II}}\text{-Cu}^{\text{II}}$ are reported by Pierre *et al.*²⁸.

Electron paramagnetic resonance :

The EPR spectra of Cu^{II} provide information of about the extent of the delocalization of the unpaired electrons. The X-band EPR spectra of the copper(II) complexes were recorded in the polycrystalline (solid state) and in solution at room temperature and their g_{\parallel} , g_{\perp} , Δg , g_{av} or g_{iso} and G were calculated.

The value of EPR parameters g_{\parallel} , g_{\perp} , g_{av} or g_{iso} , Δg , and G for copper complexes of L^1H were 2.192, 2.053, 2.103, 0.153 and 3.74, respectively for mononuclear complex **1**, whereas 2.201, 2.069, 2.085, 0.121 and 2.98, respectively for dinuclear complex **2**.

EPR spectra of the complexes revealed two g -values (g_{\parallel} and g_{\perp}). Since the g_{\parallel} and g_{\perp} values were closer to 2 and $g_{\parallel} > g_{\perp}$, a tetragonal distortion around the Cu^{II} ion is suggested. A representative EPR spectrum of both complexes was presented in Fig. 1. The trend $g_{\parallel} > g_{\perp} > g_e$ (2.0023) shows that the unpaired electron is localized in the $d_{x^2-y^2}$ orbital in the ground state of Cu^{II} and spectra were characteristic of axial symmetry. The value of $g_{\parallel} > 2.3$ is characteristic of an ionic environment and $g_{\parallel} < 2.3$ indicates a covalent environment in metal-ligand bonding. The g_{\parallel} values for the complexes were less than 2.3, suggesting the environment was covalent^{29,30}.

Fig. 1. EPR spectrum (LNT) of $[\text{Cu}(\text{L}^1)(\text{H}_2\text{O})\text{Cl}]$ **1** and $[\text{Cu}_2(\text{L}^1)_2(\text{Cl})_2]$ **2** in DMSO ($0.003 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ dm}^{-3}$) at 77 K.

In polycrystalline state, the EPR spectra are slightly orthorhombic with $g_x < g_y < g_z$ (Table 2). In solution both complexes show an axial symmetry ($g_{\parallel} > g_{\perp}$) with a $d_{x^2-y^2}$ ground state in Cu^{II} located in the square pyramidal geometry^{25,31}. The g_{\parallel} (2.192 for **1** and 2.201 for **2**) and A_{\parallel} (0.0180 cm^{-1} for **1** and 0.0195 cm^{-1} **2**) values observed for these complexes fall in the range for distorted square pyramidal geometry in the g_{\parallel} vs g_{\perp} plot³². The g_{\parallel} and A_{\parallel} values for $\text{Cu}^{\text{II}}\text{-Cu}^{\text{II}}$ binuclear complex **2** are higher and lower, respectively, than for Cu^{II} mononuclear complex **1** is retained even in solution, which is consistent with the ligand field spectral results.

The exchange coupling interaction between two Cu^{II}

Table 2. Cyclic voltammetric measurements of mononuclear and dinuclear copper complexes

Scan rate (mV/s)	E_{pc} (mV)	I_{pc} (μ A)	E_{pa} (mV)	I_{pa} (μ A)	ΔE_p (mV)	E° (mV)	I_{pa}/I_{pc} (μ A)
[Cu(L ¹)Cl].H ₂ O 1	(Mononuclear)						
100	-590	1.982	-260	1.035	330	425	0.522
200	-546	2.675	-290	2.224	256	418	0.831
[Cu ₂ (L ¹) ₂ (Cl) ₂] 2	(Dinuclear)						
100	-565	1.872	-360	1.425	205	462	0.761
	-650		-280		370		
200	-520	2.235	-385	2.021	135	452	0.904

$\Delta E_p = E_{pa} - E_{pc}$, $E^{\circ} = (E_{pa} + E_{pc})/2$.

ions is explained by the Hathaway expression :

$$G = (g_{\parallel} - 2.0023)/(g_{\perp} - 2.0023)$$

According to Hathaway³³⁻³⁵, if the value G is greater than 4 ($G > 4.0$), the exchange interaction is negligible; whereas when the value of G is less than 4 ($G < 4.0$), a considerable exchange coupling is present in a solid complex. The G values for the complexes were less than four (2.51 for mononuclear **1**, 2.80 for dinuclear **2**) indicating considerable exchange interaction in the solid state.

The EPR parameters and $d-d$ transition energies were used to evaluate the bonding parameters α^2 , β^2 and γ^2 which may be regarded as measures of the covalency of the in-plane σ -bond and the in-plane and out-of-plane π bonds respectively. The in-plane σ -bonding parameter α^2 was calculated the following expression³⁶ : $\alpha^2 = (A_{\parallel}/0.036) + (g_{\parallel} - 2.0023) + 3/7 (g_{\perp} - 2.0023) + 0.04$. The orbital reduction factors K_{\parallel} and K_{\perp} were estimated from the expression³⁷.

$K_{\parallel}^2 = (g_{\parallel} - 2.0023) E_{d-d}/8\lambda_0$, $K_{\perp}^2 = (g_{\perp} - 2.0023) E_{d-d}/2\lambda_0$, where $K_{\parallel} = \alpha^2\beta^2$, $K_{\perp} = \alpha^2\lambda^2$ and λ_0 represents the one electron spin orbit coupling constant for the free ion equal to -828 cm^{-1} . Significant information about the nature of bonding in the copper(II) complexes can be derived from the magnitude of $K_{\parallel} < K_{\perp}$. In case of pure σ -bonding, $K_{\parallel} \approx K_{\perp} \approx 0.77$ and for in-plane σ -bonding $K_{\parallel} < K_{\perp}$, while for out of plane π -bonding $K_{\parallel} > K_{\perp}$. In both copper complexes, it is observed that $K_{\parallel} > K_{\perp}$ which indicates the presence of significant out-of-plane π -bonding. The evaluated values of α^2 , β^2 and γ^2 of the complexes are consistent with both strong in-plane σ and out-of-plane π -bonding. The computed value of α^2 and β^2 (Table 3) are compared with other copper(II) com-

Table 3. EPR spectral parameters of the mononuclear and dinuclear copper complexes

Parameters	Mononuclear	Dinuclear
	1	2
Polycrystalline state (298 K)		
g_z	2.221	2.075
g_y	2.062	2.096
g_x	2.022	-
g_{iso} or g_{av}	2.102	2.085
DMSO (77 K)		
g_{\parallel}	2.192	2.201
g_{\perp}	2.053	2.069
A_{\parallel} (G)	180	195
(G)	3.74	2.98
α^2	0.848	0.879
β^2	0.164	0.161
γ^2	0.169	0.186
K_{\parallel}	0.139	0.142
K_{\perp}	0.144	0.164

plexes while are ionic in nature³⁸.

Electronic spectral study :

The electronic absorption bands in the spectra of the complexes were recorded in DMSO at 25 °C. The electronic spectrum of Cu^{II} mononuclear complex **1** of L¹H showed two bands at 715 nm and 710 nm, assignable to ${}^2B_{1g} \rightarrow {}^2B_{2g} (d_{x^2-y^2} - d_{xy})$ and ${}^2B_{1g} \rightarrow {}^2E_g (d_{x^2-y^2} \rightarrow d_{xy}, d_{yz})$ transitions, respectively. The value of magnetic moment for this complex was 1.82 B.M., square pyramidal geometry^{39,40} is suggested for the Cu^{II} complex.

Binuclear complex **2** of L¹H shows two ligand field bands, appearing at 725 nm and 716 nm, corresponding to the transitions $d_{z^2} \rightarrow d_{x^2-y^2}$ and $d_{xz} \rightarrow d_{x^2-y^2}$, respec-

tively as expected for chloride-bridged distorted square pyramidal geometry. The later band for this complex appears in the form of a broad shoulder with increased intensity, gained from the contribution of the only *d-d* absorption band due to the second copper centre of distorted square pyramidal geometry. The ligand to metal charge transfer band appeared at 430 nm, with a shoulder at 440 nm. Similar type of *d-d* bands and LMCT band were reported for a $\text{Cu}^{\text{II}}\text{-Cu}^{\text{II}}$ binuclear coordination complexes with distorted square pyramidal geometry⁸⁻¹⁰.

Infrared spectral investigation :

The IR spectrum of the complexes was compared with those of the free ligand (L^1H) in order to determine the involvement of the coordination sites in the chelation. Analysis by FT-IR results in the absorption spectra in the infrared region and register bands or signals. IR spectrum of the L^1H ligand exhibited the most characteristic bands at 1630 cm^{-1} $\nu(\text{azomethine-N})$, 1480 cm^{-1} $\nu(\text{benzenethiol-S})$ and 1320 cm^{-1} $\nu(\text{pyridine-N})$. The formation of the Schiff base, (*E*)-2-((pyridine-2-yl)methyleneamino)benzenethiol was noted from the absence of $\text{C}=\text{O}$ and NH_2 peaks in the ligands. The band at 1630 cm^{-1} due to the azomethine group of the L^1H was shifted to lower frequency ($1540\text{--}1603\text{ cm}^{-1}$) after complexation, indicating the bonding of nitrogen of the azomethine group to the Cu^{II} ion.

This can be explained by the donation of electrons from nitrogen to the empty *d*-orbital of the metal atom. A medium intensity band at 785 cm^{-1} (OH rocking) in the spectrum of mononuclear complex **1** suggests the presence of coordinated water molecule in this complex. This band was not observed in the other complexes, indicating the absence of coordinated water molecule in the binuclear complex **2**. In the low frequency region, the band of weak intensity observed^{41,42} in the spectra of the complexes in the region $522\text{--}535\text{ cm}^{-1}$ is attributed to Cu-O/Cu-S and in the region $470\text{--}490\text{ cm}^{-1}$ to Cu-N . The proposed molecular structures of the L^1H and their dinuclear (chloride-bridged) complex **2** were presented in Fig. 2 and Fig. 3, that would be helpful for versatile structural and functional properties and applications in catalysis, material research etc. The IR data of ligands and their corresponding copper complexes showed that the Schiff

Fig. 2. Proposed molecular structure of (*E*)-2-((pyridine-2-yl)-methyleneamino)benzenethiol.

Fig. 3. Proposed molecular structure of dinuclear complex $[\text{Cu}_2(\text{L}^1)_2(\text{Cl})_2]$ **2** of L^1H .

base ligand was coordinated to the Cu^{II} ion in a tridentate manner (NNS).

Cyclic voltammetry studies :

The electrochemical properties of the copper complexes of L¹H were studied by cyclic voltammetry (CV) under a nitrogen atmosphere in DMSO solution in the potential range +3.00 to -12.00 V vs an Ag/AgCl reference electrode at the scan rate 100 and 200 100 mV s⁻¹ and the results was presented in Table 2. The Cu^{II} mononuclear complex **1** of L¹H showed a reduction peak at $E_{pc} = -590$ mV with a corresponding oxidation peak at $E_{pa} = -260$ mV at a scan rate 100 mV s⁻¹. The peak separation ΔE_p was 330 mV for this couple. Thus, the cyclic voltammetric studies gave evidence to a quasi-reversible Cu^{II}/Cu^I couple. The dinuclear complex **2** of L¹H showed two reduction peaks at $E_{pc} = -540, -650$ mV with a corresponding two oxidation peaks at $E_{pa} = -360, -280$ mV, respectively at a scan rate 100 mV s⁻¹. The peak separation ΔE_p was 205 and 370 mV, respectively for this couple. The most significant feature of the Cu^{II} complexes was the Cu^{II}/Cu^I couple. This redox process was consistent with a quasi-reversible process⁴³⁻⁴⁵.

The difference in Cu^{II}/Cu^I redox potential among these complexes demonstrates that the coordination environments around the Cu^{II} ions are different and afford a substantial explanation for the difference in SOD activity of them. It is known that an adequate Cu^{II}/Cu^I redox potential for effective catalysis of superoxide radical must be required between -0.405 V versus SCE for O₂/O₂⁻ + 0.645 V versus SCE for O₂⁻/H₂O₂. The half-wave potential values for Cu^{II}/Cu^I redox couple obtained in the reaction of the copper complexes with molecular oxygen and superoxide (O₂⁻) radical elongated in DMSO are in agreement with the SOD-like activity of the copper(II) complexes.

Superoxide dismutase activity :

SOD mimetic activities of copper complexes were measured with an indirect method in which alkaline DMSO served as the source for superoxide radical. The count fraction causing 50% inhibition of NBT reduction is called IC₅₀ concentration, equivalent to one unit of SOD activity (IC₅₀ values). The IC₅₀ values of these complexes (38 μmol dm⁻³ for **1**, 34 μmol dm⁻³ for **2**) are higher than the value exhibited by the native enzyme (IC₅₀ = 0.04 μmol dm⁻³) on a molar base (note that the smaller the IC₅₀ value, the higher the SOD activity). The observed IC₅₀ values of the present complexes are compa-

rable with the various reported values for the Cu^{II} mononuclear^{46,47} and Cu₂-Cu₂-SOD or Cu₂-Zn₂-SOD dinuclear⁴⁸ complexes, but are less active than the native SOD. The higher IC₅₀ value can only be accredited to the vacant coordination sites, which facilitate the bonding of superoxide anion, electrons of aromatic ligands that stabilize Cu-O[•]- interaction and not only to the partial dissociation of complex in solution. The good activities of complexes may be attributed to the flexible nature of tridentate ligand which is able to accommodate the geometrical change from Cu^{II} to Cu^I, which are proposed to be easily substituted by the substrate O₂⁻ in the catalytic process, just like the O₂⁻, in place of H₂O bound to copper site in the mechanism of dismutation of O₂⁻ by native SOD.

Conclusion

A mononuclear complex [Cu(L¹)(H₂O)Cl] **1** and a dinuclear complex [Cu₂(L¹)₂(Cl)₂] **2**; synthesized from (*E*)-2-((pyridine-2-yl)methyleneamino)benzenethiol (L¹H) and characterized by various physico-chemical and spectroscopic techniques. IR spectra, magnetic moments, electronic spectra and EPR spectroscopic data of the complexes suggested a square pyramidal geometry for mononuclear complex **1** around Cu^{II} ion. The magnetic measurements of dicopper (chloro-bridge copper centre) complex **2** exhibited the presence of antiferromagnetic exchange interactions. The synthesized L¹H ligand was bound with the Cu^{II} ion in a tridentate manner, with SNN donor sites of the benzenethiol-S, azomethine-N, and pyridine-N atoms. The IC₅₀ values of copper complexes are higher than the value exhibited by the native enzyme (IC₅₀ = 0.04 μmol dm⁻³) on a molar base. Both the copper complexes display X-band EPR showed $d_{x^2-y^2}$ ground state.

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References

1. D. Rehder, G. Santosi, G. M. Licini, C. Schulzke and B. Meier, *Coord. Chem. Rev.*, 2003, **237**, 53.
2. S. M. Abdallah, M. A. Zayed and G. G. Mohammad, *Ara-bian J. Chem.*, 2010, **3**, 103.

3. J. M. Fraile, G. I. Garcia and J. A. Mayoral, *Chem. Rev.*, 2009, **109**, 360.
4. A. Nilgun, G. O. Selma and I. Semra, *Struct. Chem.*, 2007, **18**, 667.
5. R. K. Jain and A. P. Mishra, *J. Serb. Chem. Soc.*, 2012, **77**, 1013.
6. A. P. Mishra, N. Sharma and S. P. Srivastava, *J. Serb. Chem. Soc.*, 2009, **74**, 523.
7. (a) A. K. Pramanik, M. S. Jana and T. K. Mondal, *J. Coord. Chem.*, 2013, **66**, 4067; (b) S. Sarkar, P. K. Dhara, M. Nethaji and P. Chattopadhyay, *J. Coord. Chem.*, 2009, **62**, 817; (c) M. Kalita, P. Gogoi, P. Barman and B. Sarma, *J. Coord. Chem.*, 2014, **67**, 2445.
8. S. Kumar, R. N. Patel, P. V. Khadikar and K. B. Pandeya, *Proc. Indian Acad. Sci. (Chem. Sci.)*, 2001, **113**, 21.
9. R. N. Patel, H. C. Pandey and K. B. Pandeya, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1997, **36**, 809.
10. R. N. Patel, N. Singh, R. P. Shrivastava, S. Kumar and K. B. Pandeya, *J. Mol. Liq.*, 2000, **89**, 207.
11. P. S. Subramanian, E. Suresh and D. Shrinivas, *Inorg. Chem.*, 2010, **29**, 2053.
12. P. S. Subramanian and D. Shrinivas, *Polyhedron*, 1996, **15**, 985.
13. A. Bencini, C. Bennelli, D. Gatteschi and C. Zucchini, *Proc. Indian Acad. Sci. (Chem. Sci.)*, 1987, **13**, 98.
14. P. A. N. Reddy, M. Nethaji and A. R. Chakravarty, *Inorg. Chim. Acta*, 2003, **337**, 450.
15. U. Wesser, L. M. Schubotz and E. Lengfelder, *J. Mol. Catal.*, 1963, **13**, 249.
16. C. A. Salta, M. T. Youinou and C. T. Burrows, *Inorg. Chim. Acta*, 1991, **30**, 3454.
17. J. J. R. Frastodesilva and R. J. P. Williams, "The Biological Chemistry of the Elements", 2nd ed., Oxford University Press, Oxford, 2001.
18. I. Fridovich, *Annu. Rev. Biochem.*, 1995, **64**, 97.
19. A. F. Miller, *Comments Mol. Biophys.*, 1997, **9**, 1.
20. J. M. Mc Cord, *Superoxide Dismutase*, 2002, **349**, 331.
21. R. G. Bhirud and T. S. Shrivastava, *Inorg. Chim. Acta*, 1991, **179**, 125.
22. R. G. Bhirud and T. S. Shrivastava, *Inorg. Chim. Acta*, 1990, **179**, 121.
23. W. J. Geary, *Coord. Chem. Rev.*, 1971, **7**, 81.
24. A. P. Mishra, N. Sharma and R. Jain, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 2011, **88**, 1429.
25. R. N. Patel, *Inorg. Chim. Acta*, 2010, **363**, 3838.
26. R. N. Patel and K. B. Pandeya, *J. Inorg. Biochem.*, 1998, **72**, 109.
27. (a) M. Nandi and P. Roy, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 2013, **52**, 1263; (b) R. Priyarega, M. Temizh, S. Babu, R. Karvembu and K. Natarajan, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 2012, **51**, 453.
28. J. L. Pierre, P. Chautemps, S. Refaif, C. Beguin, A. E. Marzouki, C. Serratrache, E. Saint-Aman and P. Rey, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1995, **117**, 1965.
29. A. P. Mishra and L. R. Pandey, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 2005, **44**, 94.
30. B. Samanta, J. Chakravorty, C. R. Choudhury, S. K. Dey, S. R. Barten, P. Jensen, Glenn P. A. Yap and S. Mitra, *Struct. Chem.*, 2007, **18**, 33.
31. A. W. Addison, "Copper Coordination Chemistry", in: eds. K. D. Karlin and J.ubieta, 'Biochemical and Inorganic Perspectives', Adenine, Guiderland, New York, 1983, p. 109.
32. A. W. Addison, T. N. Rao, J. Reedijk, J. Van Rejn and G. C. Verchoor, *J. Chem. Soc., Dalton Trans.*, 1984, 1349.
33. B. J. Hathaway, *Struct. Bond. (Berlin)*, 1984, **57**, 55.
34. B. J. Hathaway and D. E. Billing, *Coord. Chem. Rev.*, 1970, **5**, 143.
35. B. J. Hathaway, in : eds. G. Wilkinson, R. D. Gilard and J. A. McCleverty, 'Comprehensive Coord. Chem.', Vol. 5, Pergamon Press, Oxford, England, 1987, 533.
36. G. F. Bryce, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1966, **70**, 3549.
37. D. X. West, *Inorg. Nucl. Chem.*, 1984, **43**, 3169.
38. B. G. Maelstrom and T. Vanngard, *J. Mol. Biol.*, 1960, **2**, 118.
39. A. B. P. Lever, "Inorganic Electronic Spectroscopy", Elsevier, Amsterdam, 1968.
40. M. Pragathi and H. Reddy, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 2013, **52**, 845.
41. K. Nakamoto, "Infrared and Raman Spectra of Inorganic and coordination compounds, Part, A and B", 5th ed., Wiley, New York, USA, 1998.
42. A. D. Kulkarni, S. A. Patil and P. S. Badami, *J. Sulf. Chem.*, 2009, **30**, 145.
43. S. Parveen and F. Arjmand, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 2005, **44**, 1151.
44. S. Gain, S. Mukhopadhyay and R. Banerjee, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 2012, **51**, 949.
45. J. Labuda, L. Fenikova and Z. Durackova, *Biochem. Bioenerg.*, 1997, **44**, 31.
46. M. Choudhary, R. N. Patel and S. P. Rawat, *J. Mol. Struct.*, 2014, **1070**, 94.
47. M. Choudhary, R. N. Patel and S. P. Rawat, *J. Mol. Struct.*, 2014, **1060**, 197.
48. (a) R. N. Patel, N. Singh, K. K. Shukla and U. K. Chauhan, *Spectrochimica Acta, Part A, Molecular and Biomelecular Spectroscopy*, 2005, **61**, 287; (b) D. Li, S. Li, D. Yang, J. Yu, J. Huang, Y. Li and W. Tang, *Inorg. Chem.*, 2003, **42**, 6071; (c) Y. H. Zhou, D. L. Sun, J. Tao, L. Q. Chen, Y. F. Huang, Y. K. Li and Y. Cheng, *J. Coord. Chem.*, 2014, **67**, 2393.